

rivojlantirishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari: dolzarbligi, muammolari va istiqbollari” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari. Qarshi, 2024. 362-368 b.

5. Nurullayeva Shaxlo Uktamovna. “Pedagogik amaliyot – bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilar metodik-refleksiv tayyorgarligining asosiy tashkiliy shakli sifatida. “yoshlarni kasb-hunarga tayyorlashning dolzarb muammolari” mavzusida xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari. Termiz, 2024.

6. Nurullayeva Shaxlo Uktamovna. Pedagogik ta‘lim jarayonini modellashtirish va loyihalashtirish yo‘llari. Zamonaviy boshlang‘ich ta‘lim: innovatsiyalar, muammolar va rivojlanish yo‘llari. Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman. Termiz. 2023. B. 23-27.

7. Nurullayeva Shaxlo Uktamovna. Innovatsion ta‘lim muhitida pedagogik modellashtirish muammolari. Tasviriy san‘at ta‘limi uzviyligini ta‘minlashning ustuvor yo‘nalishlari: muammolar va yechimlar. Xalqaro ilmiy amaliy konferensiya. Qarshi, 2023. B. 10-13.

THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON THE TRANSFORMATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN KAZAKHSTAN: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract. This paper explores the directions of artificial intelligence (AI) integration into the educational process of higher education institutions. It analyzes the three main directions of AI technology usage: systems oriented towards the faculty of higher education institutions; systems oriented towards students; and systems oriented towards the organization of the educational process as a whole. It is noted that AI serves as an auxiliary, yet valuable tool that can perform and improve a significant number of routine operations and assist in organizing an effective educational process.

Key words: higher education institutions, educational process, artificial intelligence, information and communication technologies.

Аннотация. В работе рассмотрены направления внедрения искусственного интеллекта (далее ИИ) в образовательный процесс высшего учебного заведения. Проанализированы три основные направления использования технологии ИИ: системы, ориентированные на преподавателя высшего учебного заведения; системы,

ориентированные на студента; системы, ориентированные на организацию образовательного процесса в целом. Проанализировано, что ИИ является вспомогательным, но ценным инструментом, который может выполнять и совершенствовать значительное количество рутинных операций и помогать в организации эффективного учебного процесса.

Ключевые слова: высшие учебные заведения, образовательный процесс, искусственный интеллект, информационно-коммуникационные технологии.

In recent years, the domestic higher education system has been undergoing continuous changes, driven by the need for integration into the global educational space, increasing the competitiveness of Kazakhstani educational institutions on the international stage, employer demands for the level of specialist training, and overall socio-economic changes. Modern education is transforming into an open system with a complex structure, fulfilling two main functions: creating conditions for learning and knowledge acquisition, and shaping the value orientations of future specialists.

Among the factors influencing the specifics of modern higher education, digitalization stands out. The widespread use of information and communication technologies leads to the emergence of new educational process formats, the introduction of innovative teaching methods and models of pedagogical interaction. Additionally, the integration of modern information technologies changes the very process of labor activity, leading to new professions and the creation of new jobs that require specialists to possess new knowledge and skills, and achieve new educational outcomes. This necessitates the incorporation of the latest scientific achievements into the educational process, including artificial intelligence (AI).

The aim of the study is to identify and characterize the main directions of artificial intelligence integration into the higher education system.

The methods used in this research included analysis and synthesis of the scientific literature on the topic; and studying and understanding the experience of using artificial intelligence in education.

Overall, the use of AI technology in the higher education system can be analyzed in three directions:

- Systems oriented towards higher education faculty;
- Systems oriented towards students;
- Systems oriented towards the use of artificial intelligence in education as a whole [1].

AI technologies aimed at university educators are utilized to support teachers and alleviate their workload by automating tasks such as administration, grading, feedback, plagiarism detection, and more. The use of

artificial intelligence in an educator's role can be divided into two unequal but interconnected directions. The first relates to employing AI to organize the educational process, while the second pertains to the educational process itself, altering the interactions between instructors and students. The first direction is considerably easier for employing AI algorithms and is akin to its application in fields associated with automating routine actions and processes. The second direction develops and is implemented much more slowly because it must simulate the live, creative communication between students and professors. Nevertheless, the development and implementation of the first direction positively influence the second.

J. Klutka and others contend that AI can manage many routine functions currently performed by teachers and educational administrators, thus freeing them to address more complex issues and interact with students on deeper levels. This presents an opportunity for a new role for the university instructor, whose activity will be focused on developing students' skills and competencies [2]. However, as studies indicate, this claim remains too optimistic for the time being. Many aspects of this are due to the fact that the majority of AI developments for teaching, education, and research are made by programmers, not educators [3]. These systems are created and developed based on the capabilities and visions of AI technology developers, rather than the needs of the educational process.

Today in European countries, artificial intelligence technologies are widely used to review student responses in feedback surveys [4]. This allows for saving up to 80% of human effort (approximately two weeks of a teacher's work) compared to performing this task manually.

The use of proctoring systems is also promising. These systems are capable of analyzing student behavior during remote assessments: the frequency of looking away from the monitor, attempts to switch browser tabs, the presence of other people or voices, etc. [5].

Analyzing artificial intelligence systems, it can be said that they can already be effectively used for:

1. Providing feedback between teachers and students;
2. Monitoring each student's academic progress;
3. Assessing students' knowledge and skills, which allows educators to tailor the learning process to their level of preparation;
4. Using intelligent mentors to provide educational content;
5. Offering specialized support and increasing awareness of knowledge gaps, enabling teachers to more effectively educate through personalized and adaptive learning;

6. Analyzing audience dynamics and student engagement, which helps identify at-risk students in real time, allowing for timely intervention.

Artificial intelligence is currently used as a personal assistant for writing and analyzing texts, studying foreign languages, organizing work schedules, etc. At present, students are actively using text services that allow them to create content based on artificial intelligence. The most common systems in modern education are AI systems capable of interpreting language, analyzing the emotional tone of sentences, and automatically translating into other languages without losing meaning; personal recommendations, based on the user's previous experience and that of their friends, help students make optimal choices regarding educational programs, as well as friends, teachers, relevant literature, etc. Another way AI is utilized is in organizing learning based on the trial and error method – this is a quite effective technique for consolidating skills, as this process lacks clear instructions and the student intuitively seeks the most effective ways to solve problems.

AI systems can meet one of UNESCO's fundamental demands in the education system – making education accessible to all. There have long been programs that convert spoken language into text, which is very relevant for people with poor vision (for example, the Dragon Anywhere platform).

Artificial intelligence has all the means to make the student learning process personalized and adaptive. Adaptive learning involves selecting educational content according to the needs of each student with varying levels of preparation, with the ability to track progress in learning and alter its trajectory based on outcomes. AI takes into account the methodology and pace of material absorption, the needs of each student, their personal interests and preferences, and selects tasks of increasing complexity. Personalization of learning is successfully implemented in the Thinkster system. Users of the platform undergo testing, after which AI provides a preliminary learning plan.

AI technologies also positively impact the sphere of upbringing, using monitoring and control functions. For instance, Google's smartphone app Bark provides a set of tools for parenting in the digital age. It can "monitor" data exchange platforms and email, social networks, YouTube, and other services popular among teenagers, with the aim of detecting signs of bullying, cyber threats, depression, suicidal thoughts, etc.

A third important direction in the use of artificial intelligence in higher education is the administration of educational processes. For example, Factspan Analytics Inc. offers solutions for a whole complex of tasks, automating processes such as student adaptation; knowledge assessment; tracking absences; report keeping and auditing; various office tasks (certification of educational programs, teacher certification, payroll, etc.).

Despite the above, the use of AI technology in the higher education system has not yet elevated it to a qualitatively new level. AI has not yet aided in the development of higher-order skills, critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and knowledge management among students. AI is a supportive, yet valuable tool that can perform and enhance a large number of various operations conducted at universities, assist in organizing effective educational processes, and in building necessary communications.

At the same time, it should be noted that the promising directions for the use of AI in higher education are not limited to the above. Overall, many issues regarding the interaction of artificial intelligence with the higher education system require further research. How should the learning process change under new conditions? What focus should professors have in teaching? On developing those competencies that robots and AI lack: creativity, teamwork skills, leadership qualities. Or on teaching students to interact better with artificial intelligence, potential forms of collaboration between specialists and AI in solving common problems. For the latter, it is necessary to better understand the capabilities of AI thinking, the "different logic" of interaction between the teacher and artificial intelligence, as opposed to colleagues.

References

1. Baker T., Smith L. Educ-AI-tion rebooted? Exploring the future of artificial intelligence in schools and colleges. Retrieved from Nesta Foundation website. [Электронный ресурс]. URL: https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/Future_of_AI_and_education_v5_WEB.pdf.
2. Klutka J. et al. Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education: Current Uses and Future Applications. – Louisville: Learning house, 2018.
3. Zawacki-Richter O., Marín V.I., Bond M., Gouverneur F. Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education – where are the educators? // International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education. – 2019. – № 1. – doi: 10.1186/s41239-019-0171-0.
4. Nawaz Raheel, Quanbin Sun, Matthew Shardlow, Georgios Kontonatsios, Naif R. Aljohani, Anna Visvizi, Saeed-Ul Hassan Leveraging AI and Machine Learning for National Student Survey: Actionable Insights from Textual Feedback to Enhance Quality of Teaching and Learning in UK's Higher Education // Applied Sciences. – 2022. – № 1. – p. 514. – doi: 10.3390/app12010514.
5. Абыканова Б.Т. и др. Системы на основе искусственного интеллекта в педагогическом образовании: возможности и последствия // Вестник Атырауского университета имени Халела Досмухамедова. – 2024. – Т. 71. – №. 4. – С. 59-72.